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Impact Of Social Networking Usage On Adolescents' Psychosocial Behaviours: A Correlational Study Of Senior Secondary School Students In Obio/Akpor Local Government Area In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the impact of social networking usage on adolescents' psychosocial behaviours in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. Correlational research design was used for the study. The population consisted of 6,344 (3,584 females and 2,760 males) students from 20 public senior secondary schools, with a sample size of 560 students selected through simple random sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled Social Networking and Psychosocial Scale (SNPS), which consisted of three sections: the Social Networking Scale (SNS), the Internet Addiction Table (IAT), and the Peer Group Scale (PGS). The reliability coefficients of the instruments, as determined using the Cronbach Alpha method, were 0.66 for SNS, 0.76 for IAT, and 0.72 for PGS, indicating acceptable levels of internal consistency. Two research questions and its corresponding null hypotheses formulated and postulated guided this study. The data collected were analyzed using simple regression method, while the null hypotheses were tested with analysis of variance (ANOVA) and t-test associated with regression at an alpha level of 0.05 significance. The finding showed that internet addiction and peer group influence can significantly predict social networking usage among adolescent. Based on the findings it was recommended that government should as a matter of importance, engage the services of guidance counsellors in all our secondary schools, especially in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area to assist students deal with psychosocial problems relating to Social Networking and teachers, parents and guidance counsellors should help students manage their time properly by giving assignments to keep students busy and also setting attainable goals, this will help reduce the rate if not totally eradicate psychosocial behaviours relating to social networking in secondary school.

Keywords: Social networking, Internet addiction, Peer group influence, Psychosocial behaviour, Adolescents.

INTRODUCTION

Social networking sites is the most sorts after sites on the web today. This has contributed a lot to our adolescent long stay online in sites such as Twitter, YouTube, Face book, Myspace and a host of others too numerous to mention. Some people believe that excessive use of social networking sites could be responsible for various psychosocial behaviors in adolescents, such as internet addiction, anxiety, depression, peer group influence, strained parental relationships, academic underachievement, low self-

concept, and low self-esteem. Could this really be the case? Observing adolescents in classrooms, lecture halls, on the roads, and in vehicles, we often notice them fully engrossed with both hands on their phones or tablets, distracted from their surroundings. What are they doing? They are either chatting or sourcing information on the web through social networking sites. Agosto & Abbas, (2017), look at social networking sites as communication tools where youths reason together and keep in touch with one another.

There are positive aspects of social media use among students, and also there are equally as many negative effects concerning the use of such gadgets. Since their introduction, social networking sites have drawn the attention of many adolescents and university students as observed by (Lenhart & Madden, 2019). The manner in which these sites are paving their ways through the educational setting cannot be over emphasized, hence the belief that these sites have even more potential for the improvement of teaching, learning and sharing of information among learners as well as educators (Ferdig, 2007). Social media have positively impacted in so many ways in human life thereby connecting millions of people from all over the globe; also, the use of these sites has another impact as an interactive world full of ideas, insight, and opinions. It acts as an aid for school work, in the sense that students have a wide range of information, knowledge and experience to learn from and to report on. Flad (2010) asserted that internet when used as a tool, has many advantages in sharing and cognitive innovation among teachers and students.

It has been observed that excessive use of social networking sites tends to have negative consequences on students' well-being, including sleep disturbances, feelings of despair, and dejection. It also results in disruptive behaviours that negatively impact the teaching and learning process, thereby hindering students from benefiting fully from classroom instruction (Amaechi-Udogu & Oveneshi, 2020). Such students also exhibit more of egotistic tendencies and other disorders related to personality, including other antisocial behaviours as well as hostile tendencies. Frequent use of these sites leads to addiction that inculcates bad habits, and also vulnerability to crime, these results from lack of privacy, and insecurity activities such as hacking, blackmailing, racketeering, fraud, impersonation, scam publishing, and blogs. Also, criminals like robbers can easily get information on individuals' activities via social media search, Sexual harassment and assaults sexting or pornography (messaging or picturing sexual form), and cyber-bullying (the use of electronic communication to harass an individual, usually by sending intimidating or threatening mails) through social media network. Research has shown that adolescents are mostly influenced by the type of social media or network they subscribe to; thus, internet dependence significantly affects students' academic performance and emotional traits negatively (Asemah et al., 2013; Umar & Idris, 2018). These studies report that this negative influence is most prominent among extreme users of the internet and not on all individuals.

Areas of concern related to the negative effects of adolescent social media use include cyberbullying, exposure to inappropriate content, sleep deprivation, Internet addiction, 'Facebook depression', and social isolation (Barth, 2015; Kwan et al., 2020; O'Keeffe & Clarke-Pearson, 2011). Potential areas of benefit have also been noted, including self-expression, self-exploration, information, and communication technology (ICT) skill development, and international networking (Barth, 2015; Ivie et al., 2020; Sarriera et al., 2012).

Addiction is a primary, chronic disease of brain reward, motivation, memory, and related circuitry. It is reflected in the individual's pursuit of reward and/or relief through substance use and other behaviors. Addiction is characterized by impairments in behavioral control, cravings, an inability to consistently abstain, and diminished recognition of significant problems with one's behaviors and interpersonal relationships. According to the American Society of Addiction Medicine (2019), a person can become addicted to any substance, whether legal or illegal, as well as any behavior that the individual finds gratifying. Addiction is considered a mental illness and can be treated in a manner similar to other mental health disorders, through therapy, medication, and lifestyle changes. Addiction is both psychological and behavioral. Addictions are characterized by craving, compulsion, an inability to stop the addictive behavior, and lifestyle dysfunction resulting from the substance or behavior use.

Behavioural addictions are those addictions that substances are not used. This type of addiction can be an impulse control disorder as defined in the DSM-IV-TR or an addiction identified by an addiction professional (American Psychiatric Association 2013). Behavioural addictions outside of the DSM-IV-TR are controversial and many don't feel they meet the requirement of being an official addiction. The researcher here is concern with internet addiction.

Greenfield (2007) describes internet addiction as a socially connecting device that paradoxically results in social isolation. It enables individuals to communicate with others while simultaneously preventing them from engaging in face-to-face social interactions. Internet addiction is regarded as an impulse-control problem, characterized by an individual's inability to resist the urge to stay online for prolonged periods. It is often associated with psychological challenges such as loneliness, depression, and anxiety. Internet addiction is perceived to have both psychological and sociological implications, with some scholars describing it as a journey to an unknown destination. Individuals affected by internet addiction tend to spend a considerable amount of time online, which leads to withdrawal from important real-life activities, including family interactions, social engagements, work responsibilities, and even attention to personal health. Furthermore, internet addiction has been identified as a contributing factor to family breakups, marital conflicts, and the decline of promising careers.

Internet addiction has not only made its users withdrawn from the society but has also provided them with the opportunity to engage and encourage deviant behaviours such as online criminal acts of downloading and viewing illegal sites like pornography, deception and even indulge in aggressive online activities e.g. playing of computer games. It further avails them the opportunity to communicate with strangers behind the screen, thus losing real life communication skills thereby making them more socially withdrawn. Obviously, since these adolescents are exposed to different social networking sites and they also differ in their level of usage, it is plausible that their psychosocial behaviours may depend partly on their social networking usage.

Another variable under study is peer group influence. According to the American Psychological Association (APA, 2018), a peer group is "a group of individuals who share one or more characteristics, such as age, social status, economic status, occupation, or education." Members of a peer group are likely to influence an individual's beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours. Peer groups are characterized by hierarchies and distinct patterns of behaviour, where members typically belong to the same age group, social strata, and share common interests. Adolescents, in particular, tend to spend more time with their peers and experience reduced adult supervision (Steinberg, 2018). Furthermore, children are less likely to associate with individuals who are different from them in terms of behaviour or interests. Peer groups play a significant role in identity development, as they facilitate independence from parental control and provide support for young people as they establish adult relationships and set personal life goals (Griffiths, 1997). McPherson et al. (2001) further emphasize the role of homophily in peer group formation, noting that individuals tend to form strong social ties with others who are similar in characteristics like age, education, and social status, which strengthens the influence of peer groups on socialization and behavior. People use the social networking sites for various reasons. Mogbel (2012) believes that Internet technological advancement has revolutionized communication. Coyle (2018) also supports this view that this communication revolution, apart from technologically empowering individual, user's lifestyle it has changed the way people connect and communicate with each other.

Mech and Talmud (2017) in Israel found out relationships developed offline is stronger than those developed online. This supports the view that online friendships and relationship are not seen as a replacement. Technologies are used to enable social relationship using the available devices. This Ellison, Steinfeld and Lampe (2017) show that in using social networking site, Facebook show that those with weak ties develop social relationship positively.

Existing systematic reviews on social media impacts tend to focus on a select subset of psychosocial dimensions, for example, body image and eating disorders (Holland & Tiggemann, 2016), depression (Ivie et al., 2020), or general mental health outcomes (Frost & Rickwood, 2017; Keles et al., 2020; Kwan et al., 2020). Some of the existing reviews include mixed or undifferentiated developmental groups, with

Ivie et al. (2020), Keles et al. (2020), and Valkenburg and Peter (2011) focusing exclusively on adolescents. The review by Valkenburg and Peter (2011) appears to be the most recent review focusing on the impact of social media on a broader conceptualization of psychosocial development among adolescents. There is a need to synthesize recent evidence of the broader developmental impact of social media on adolescents (Barth, 2015). The present study is on how social networking has a relationship on the adolescent psychosocial behaviors of students in Obio/Akpor Local government area of Rivers State

Statement of Problem

The rise of social networking sites has significantly influenced the psychosocial development of adolescents, with both positive and negative effects. While these platforms offer several benefits, such as the dissemination of information, opportunities for e-learning, knowledge sharing, and fostering social capital through guided connectivity, they also have potential drawbacks. Excessive usage of these sites has been linked to negative consequences, including loss of concentration, distraction, depression, poor communication skills, and the replacement of face-to-face interactions with online messaging. These impacts raise concerns about the influence of social networking on adolescents' mental health and well-being.

In addition to the psychosocial issues, social networking sites have been shown to contribute to behavioral problems, with adolescents often spending excessive time online at the expense of studying, family engagement, and physical health. The personal information shared on these platforms, including profiles and locations, poses a significant privacy risk, making adolescents vulnerable to both known and unknown individuals. Consequently, experts argue that parents, educators, and internet safety managers should closely monitor online activities and encourage responsible use of social media.

The rapid growth of internet subscriptions in Nigeria has further heightened these concerns. Reports from the National Communications Commission (NCC) indicated a sharp increase in internet subscriptions to 50 million between February and March 2022. This surge suggests that adolescents, particularly those in secondary schools, are becoming more dependent on these social networking platforms. The potential dangers of online engagement, including exposure to online predators and the psychosocial impact of excessive use, are becoming more prominent.

Although much research on social networking sites and adolescent behavior has been conducted outside Nigeria, there is a notable lack of studies focusing on Nigerian adolescents, particularly those in secondary schools in Port Harcourt. This study sought to fill this gap by investigating how social networking sites, such as Facebook, Twitter, and others, relate to adolescents' affective behaviors, particularly in terms of internet addiction and peer group influence.

Aims and Objectives of study

The aim of the study was to find out whether social networking has a relationship on the adolescent psychosocial behaviors of students in Obio/Akpor Local government area of Rivers State. The study specifically:

1. Find out the relationship between social networking and adolescents' internet addiction
2. Find out the relationship between social networking and adolescents' peer group influence.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study

1. Is there an impact of social networking usage on adolescent internet addiction?
2. Is there an impact of adolescents' social networking usage and peer group Influence?

Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 levels of significance.

1. There is no significant impact of adolescents' social networking usage on internet addiction.
2. There is no significant impact adolescents' social networking usage on adolescent peer group influence.

METHODOLOGY

The Correlational research design was adopted in the study. This design is considered appropriate since the researchers’ interested was to investigate the impact social networking usage on adolescents’ psychosocial variables. The population for this study consists of all the senior secondary school students in SS II in the 20 public Senior Secondary Schools in Obio/Apkor Local Government Area, with a total number 3,584 female and 2,760 males (that is 6,344 students). The sample size for the study was 560 Senior Secondary School Students (SSII). Simple random sampling technique was employed to randomly select the students. Simple random sampling technique was adopted because it gives all the members of the population equal tendency to be part of the sample size. The researcher-made instruments titled “Social Networking and Psychosocial Scale (SNPS) was used for data collection. The instruments consisted of three parts; Social Networking Usage, Internet Addiction Test (IAT), and Peer Group Scale (PGS) which are made up of 10 items each. The instruments were scored using a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The instrument was subjected to face and content validity while Cronbach alpha was used to check the internal consistency of the instrument to guarantee the use of the instrument for the study. With a reliability coefficient of 0.66, 0.76 and 0.72 respectively. Data collected was analysed using Simple regression Statistic in Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The r- Value (coefficient) of Simple regression Statistic was used to answer the research questions based on the scale interpretation while the null hypotheses was tested using significance value in Simple regression Statistic at .05 alpha level of significance.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Research Question 1: *Is there an impact of social networking usage on adolescent internet addiction?*

Table 1: Simple Regression Analysis on the impact of social networking usage on adolescent internet addiction

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.275 ^a	.076	.074	5.37570

In table 1, the regression analysis revealed a moderate positive relationship between social networking usage and adolescent internet addiction, as indicated by an R-value of 0.275. The R-squared value of 0.076 suggests that approximately 7.6% of the variation in adolescent internet addiction can be explained by the level of social networking usage. Judging by the coefficient of determination, this means that 7.6% of the change in adolescents’ use of social networking can be impacted by internet addiction, while the remaining 92.4% of the variation is accounted for by other variables not considered in this study. This suggests a relatively weak but positive impact of social networking usage on adolescent internet addiction.

The standard error of the estimate (5.37570) indicates the average distance between the observed values and the predicted values by the regression model. This reveals a moderate level of prediction accuracy.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant impact of adolescents’ social networking usage on internet addiction.

Table 2: t-test associated with simple regression showing the impact of social networking usage on internet addiction

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	22.886	.713		32.101	.000
	IAT	.219	.032	.275	6.752	.000

a. Dependent Variable SNS

Results from Table 2 revealed that in model 1, where social networking usage (SNS) was the independent variable, the Beta value was 0.275, indicating a moderate positive relationship between social networking usage and internet addiction. The t-value for SNS was 6.752, which was statistically significant at the 0.000 level ($p < 0.05$), lower than the chosen significance level of 0.05. This suggests that social networking usage significantly impacts adolescent internet addiction. Specifically, as social networking usage increases, the level of internet addiction among adolescents also increases. The R-squared value of 0.076 indicates that social networking usage accounts for approximately 7.6% of the variation in internet addiction. The regression equation for this model is $Y' = 22.886 + 0.219 X_1$, where X_1 represents the Social Networking Usage score and Y' represents the predicted internet addiction score. Based on these findings, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Research Question 2: *Is there an impact of adolescents' social networking usage and peer group Influence?*

Table 3: Simple Regression Analysis on the impact of adolescents' social networking usage and peer group Influence?

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.329 ^a	.108	.104	5.28849

The regression analysis in Table 3 reveals a positive relationship between adolescents' social networking usage (SNS) and peer group influence, with an R value of 0.329. The R-squared value of 0.108 suggests that 10.4% of the variation in peer group influence can be explained by adolescents' social networking usage. The remaining 89.6% of the variation is attributed to other factors not considered in the study.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant impact of adolescents' social networking usage on adolescent peer group influence.

Table 4: t-test associated with simple regression showing the impact of adolescents' social networking usage on adolescent peer group influence.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients			Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	19.494	1.035		18.831	.000
	PGI	.110	.047	.114	2.353	.019

a. Dependent Variable SNS

Table 4 shows the results of the t-test for the regression model. The Beta value for social networking usage (SNS) is 0.114, indicating a moderate positive relationship between social networking usage and peer group influence. The t-value for social networking usage is 2.353, and the p-value is 0.019, which is less than the chosen significance level of 0.05. This indicates that social networking usage has a statistically significant impact on peer group influence.

Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that social networking usage significantly influences peer group influence among adolescents. The regression equation for this model is $Y' = 19.494 + 0.110 X_1$, where X_1 is the score on social networking usage, and Y' is the predicted peer group influence score.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

The results of the finding revealed that Social Networking usage is strong significant predictor of Internet Addiction. It means that the higher the involvement in Social Networking Usage the higher the Internet Addiction. The result revealed that Internet Addiction was the first variable to be included in the model and that it had the highest and significant contribution of 7.6% variations in the Social Networking Usage among adolescents as seen in its R^2 value of 0.076 and beta value of 0.275. Based on the positive Beta

value, it is deduced that as the level of Internet Addiction increases among adolescents their Social Networking Usages also increased. However, this finding of significant prediction of Social Networking Usage on Internet Addiction is not surprising but expected. This is because an addicted individual finds it difficult to stop the behaviour, he/she is addicted to. Rather the person will always have the urge to put up the behaviour. That is the individual will always have an impulse control problem towards the behaviour addicted to. Furthermore, this finding is to some extent similar to that of Chou and Hsio (2016). They found that Internet prediction was only related to perceived impact on studies and daily routines. The similarity between both findings may be due to the facts that daily routines of life may include Social Networking Usages in this computer age. In another dimension, this finding from the present study contradicted that of Chak and Leung's (2014). They found that Internet Addiction was associated with shyness. This disparity between both findings may be as a result of the use of Social Networking Usage instead of shyness.

The results in table 3 and 4 revealed that Peer Group Influence significantly predicted Social Networking Usage with a beta value of 0.114 with the corresponding t-value of 2.353 which was significant at 0.019 level. Furthermore, the positive beta value of 0.114 for Peer Group Influence indicated that as the level of Peer Group Influence increases among the adolescents their level of Social Networking Usages also increased. This finding is expected not surprising due to the attributes of individuals with high level of Peer Group Influence. It is believed that high level of Peer Group Influence exerts high pressure on individuals into changing his/her behaviour to match that of his/her peers. Consequently, this finding may be attributed to the fact that Social Networking creates an enabling environment and opportunity for the adolescents to chat, e-mail, play online games, share files, photos, videos, exchange views and interest hence the adolescents get involved in Social Networking usage. This finding is not in line with that of Allen et al (2018), they found that Peer Group is the primary resource for emotional support; hence the adolescents learn from their peers and also maintain intimate friendships and other social skills.

CONCLUSIONS

The study explored the impact of social networking usage on adolescents' psychosocial behaviors, specifically focusing on senior secondary school students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. The findings reveal that social networking usage has a statistically significant impact adolescents' internet addiction and peer group influence. It was observed that social networking usage accounted for a moderate percentage of the variations in internet addiction and peer group influence among the adolescents, demonstrating a positive correlation between these variables. The results suggest that while social networking sites offer opportunities for connection and engagement, their excessive use can contribute to negative psychosocial behaviors, including internet addiction and increased peer group influence.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. The government should ensure the employment of qualified guidance counsellors in all secondary schools within Obio/Akpor Local Government Area to help students manage psychosocial challenges associated with social networking.
2. Teachers, parents, and counsellors should guide students in effective time management by assigning meaningful tasks and setting achievable goals to minimize negative behaviours linked to excessive social networking.
3. The Rivers State Post Primary Education Board, in collaboration with school authorities, should organize regular workshops and seminars to educate students on the appropriate use, benefits, and potential risks of social networking.
4. Awareness campaigns should be conducted in schools to sensitize students on the dangers of excessive social networking usage, including internet addiction and mental health challenges. Counsellors and teachers should lead these initiatives to promote responsible social media use.

5. Schools should strengthen counselling services to support students dealing with psychosocial issues such as peer pressure, low self-esteem, and addiction arising from social networking. Counsellors should be adequately trained and resourced for this purpose.
6. Parents should actively monitor and guide their children's use of social media by setting reasonable time limits, encouraging healthy online behaviours, and promoting alternative recreational and educational activities.
7. School management and educational authorities should develop clear policies regulating students' use of social networking sites during school hours, ensuring a balance between online engagement and academic focus to support students' holistic development.

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